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When Hurricanes Go Viral: The influence of social media on Eastern North Carolinians' evacuation decision making

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This study describes a questionnaire survey of residents in Eastern North Carolina. The survey was conducted to assess Eastern North Carolina residents' social media habits, their perception of risk to extreme weather events, how they use social media to decide whether to follow evacuation orders, and their trust in authorities during a crisis.

Eastern North Carolina is a high-risk area that is uniquely vulnerable to hurricanes and flooding. Despite mandatory evacuation orders, many people in high-risk areas like Eastern North Carolina do not evacuate. There is a multitude of personal, social, and experiential factors that go into the evacuation decision making process. Social media has become a popular information source people seek to determine their level of risk to a disaster. This study seeks to understand the implications of social media use for evacuation decision making and its potential influence on perceptions of risk to crises.

Headings:

Social Media

Evacuation Decision Making

Fake News

WHEN HURRICANES GO VIRAL: THE INFLUENCE OF SOCIAL MEDIA ON
EASTERN NORTH CAROLINIANS' EVACUATION DECISION MAKING

by
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INTRODUCTION

Eastern North Carolina is considered a high-risk area for natural disasters, especially hurricanes and flooding. The way North Carolina's coast extends out makes it one of the nation's most open areas to a direct hurricane strike. In the last 20 years, every area of the state has been impacted by hurricanes, causing widespread damage and subsequent severe weather including tornadoes, flooding, storm surges, and landslides (Ready NC, *Hurricanes*). One of the most devastating hurricanes was Hurricane Florence, which was the costliest and wettest hurricane on record for North Carolina (Davis, 2020). Despite mandatory evacuation orders and numerous warnings about disastrous flooding from officials, many people in high-risk areas of the state did not evacuate (Resnick, 2018). There were a variety of reasons why people chose not to evacuate, including financial, disabilities, and pets. There were also people who said they were concerned about leaving their property for fear of potential damage and looting, as well as people who had previous experience with hurricanes and were confident in their ability to ride out the storm (Resnick, 2018). This kind of behavior has implications for research focused on how risk is perceived and communicated, particularly for studying evacuation decision making. This study seeks to understand how this behavior is influenced by social media.

Recent studies indicate social media is changing the way people respond to and prepare for natural disasters, including evacuation decision making; yet research of the

role social media plays in influencing peoples' perception of risk during a disaster is limited. Evacuation decision making is now more heavily influenced by media and other personal characteristics. While modern forecasting technology and warning systems have significantly advanced, natural disasters can still be unpredictable. As a result, people have more difficulty understanding their risk to natural disasters and their options for preparedness. Existing research on evacuation decision making demonstrates that a multitude of factors go into this process, and that behavior in hurricane evacuations is constantly evolving due to emerging issues such as stronger storms, changes in how people receive and interpret warning information, and the rise of social media use for disaster response (Bowser & Cutter, 2015).

Warnings alone do not motivate evacuation, people must also perceive they have a risk to a disaster (Dash & Galdwin, 2007). People can listen to the same warning but perceive it differently. Although people generally agree that there is a need for greater preparedness, they do not perceive this as applying to them (Johnston et al., 1999). If information is not communicated in such a way that clearly translates pending danger and imminent threat, people's perception of risk can change (Baker et al., 2012; Dash & Galdwin, 2007; Mishra & Mazumdar, 2015). Crisis authorities play a significant role in addressing ambiguous or false narratives. If there is a lack of coordination around crisis communication to the affected populations, this can threaten timely and accurate delivery of disaster responses, as well as confuse residents (Cheong & Babcock, 2020).

In summation, the research indicates that awareness of a threat or disaster does not necessarily lead to preventative actions to prepare for the disaster. The assumption that education leads to awareness is essentially a myth as this does not always occur

(Sims & Baumann, 1983). Despite the wealth of research on emergency preparedness and response, little research has demonstrated the role social media plays in this decision-making process.

As the use of social media applications in disaster preparedness increases, there is also the risk of false or contradictory information being spread. About 36% of U.S. adults say they regularly use Facebook as a source of news, making it the most widely used social media application for news, next to YouTube and Twitter (Gramlich, 2021). The ability of social media to spread information quickly is also leading to a rapid spread of rumors and misinformation, creating a critical issue that is exacerbated during public emergencies (Bowser & Cutter, 2015). With its rapid dissemination of information about disasters, social media is changing how people find information to confirm their risk to extreme weather events, yet few studies have attempted to measure its influence on risk perceptions (Bowser & Cutter, 2015; Tran et al., 2020).

Eastern North Carolina was chosen for this study due to its clear geographical limits and its unique vulnerability to storms and urban development. This study seeks to understand whether social media influences Eastern North Carolina residents' evacuation decision making through a quantitative survey that assesses their experiences with disasters and social media habits. Results support existing research that show how social media has become a widely used source of information during disasters, and that the increasing spread of misinformation within these digital networked environments poses a risk to vital decision-making processes.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The psychology of disaster preparedness and evacuation decision making

For years ecopsychologists have studied how humans respond to and prepare for disasters. A response to a disaster or threat is known as a “psychological adaptation” (Mishra & Mazumdar, 2015). Factors that influence response to climate change are similar to factors that influence disaster preparedness, such as perceived risk and disaster cognition. There are three interactive predictors of environmental behavior: intrapersonal (personality and motivations), interpersonal (social norms), and external (rewards and punishment) (Mishra & Mazumdar, 2015). Other factors influencing disaster preparedness behavior include peoples' characteristics, psychological qualities, reaction to risk and hazard, prior experience, knowledge, resources, and action (Mishra & Mazumdar, 2015).

A psychological quality known as ‘the locus of control’ has been commonly mentioned in research on disaster preparedness behaviors. There are two types of ‘the locus control’: internal and external. Internal locus of control describes people who feel their fate or destiny is in their control and are typically more prepared for disasters, while people with external locus of control believe external forces determine their fate and tend to be less prepared (Mishra & Mazumdar, 2015; Sims & Baumann, 1983). For example, people with internal locus of control are more likely to buy flood insurance than those with an external locus (Sims & Baumann, 1983).

Research has suggested that awareness of a threat or disaster does not necessarily lead to preventative actions to prepare for the disaster, and that education does not **always** lead to greater awareness. Studies have shown that education of a disaster **may** lead to awareness, which **may** lead to disaster preparedness behavior (Baker et al., 2012; Mishra & Mazumdar, 2015; Sims & Baumann, 1983). The reasons behind this phenomenon are still being studied, however current research has found that a body of psychological characteristics, such as peoples' values, motivations, beliefs, and attitudes, influences how they respond to and prepare for disasters (Sims & Baumann, 1983).

Peoples' experiences with hurricanes and other extreme weather events does not necessarily mean they have a greater perception of risk to future events. The relationship between hazard experience and preventative response is considered more conditional (Sims & Baumann, 1983). Some studies have shown that people with prior experience wait longer to evacuate than those that do not (Baker et al., 2012). Sims and Baumann support this finding and note that hazard experiences raise peoples' "threshold levels," which dictate the point in time when a person is satisfied with the information regarding evacuation orders (Sims & Baumann, 1983).

Peoples' past experiences with disasters can also bias their perceptions of future hazards. Their experience may be limited to biased, or they were not negatively affected by a past disaster and therefore conclude they are not vulnerable to any future disasters (Baker et al., 2012; Sims & Baumann, 1983). Some researchers also refer to this as the "crying wolf" hypothesis, which has been cited as a reason why many residents in high-risk areas don't evacuate. The hypothesis states that individuals who have experienced disasters that were not as severe as predicted begin to discount any validity of future

warnings. This mindset can also contribute to a “disaster subculture,” which includes individuals that are aware of a perceived threat but do not evacuate (Burnside et al., 2007).

People are also less likely to evacuate if they perceive a storm is weak or that the worst of it will miss them (Bowser & Cutter, 2015). Given the right conditions, lower rated storms like Category 1 and 2, even tropical storms, can still produce significant damage (Bowser & Cutter, 2015). Research has also shown that people can easily misinterpret the track of a hurricane, sometimes to such an extent that they believe their community would be severely impacted. It should be noted that some of the costliest and deadliest hurricanes to hit the North Carolina coast landed as a Category 1, including Hurricane Florence, Matthew, and Dorian. Research has shown that reliance on the Saffir-Simpson scale (a hurricane wind scale) as the only source for evacuation decision making is problematic. In cases when damage did not occur, it’s postulated that complacency set in among evacuees, leading to evacuation failure (i.e., remaining when there is danger) (Bowser & Cutter, 2015).

While previous experiences can influence how people receive warning information, lack of clear communication and confusion around the information can also affect how warnings are received. During Hurricane Sandy, there was widespread confusion about the warnings being issued, leaving many people ill-prepared. For example, some coastal residents believed the biggest threat of Sandy was from the wind rather than the storm surge and did not take necessary protective actions (Baker et al., 2012). Part of the source of confusion was due to the decision by the National Hurricane Center to not issue hurricane watches or warnings along the Mid-Atlantic or New

England, and instead allowed local weather service offices to issue watches and warnings for high winds, coastal flooding, etc. This also created confusing messaging around what kind of storm Sandy was; the National Hurricane Center referred to it as a hurricane until landfall while the mass media used names such as “Superstorm Sandy” and “Frankenstorm Sandy” (Baker et al., 2012). The more specific warning information is, the more likely people perceive their risk to a hurricane, and the more likely it will be heard and believed (Dash & Galdwin, 2007).

Warnings alone do not motivate evacuation, people must also perceive they have a risk to a disaster (Dash & Galdwin, 2007). Perceived risk is considered one of the most important factors when determining evacuation behavior. Research on cognitive complexity and framing has shown that when people feel personally threatened, they spend more time searching for information in times of uncertainty. Most of the research on evacuation behavior indicates that when people utilize more information sources, the likelihood they will evacuate increases (Burnside et al., 2007). If people do not believe warnings or that their risk to the threat is real, then any probability of an adaptive response decreases (Baker et al., 2012; Dash & Galdwin, 2007). Additional factors that influence risk perceptions and evacuation decision making include cultural and demographic factors, such as gender, race, and income (Bowser & Cutter, 2015). People who have fewer resources may find it harder to evacuate in the event of a disaster (Bowser & Cutter, 2015).

Evacuation decision making is now more heavily influenced by media and other personal characteristics. People personalize their risk to events by seeking information from different sources, such as the authorities, news media, peers, family, and co-

workers; to interpret warning information and determine their level of risk (Bowser & Cutter, 2015; Dash & Galdwin, 2007; Sadri et al., 2017). The process of seeking information to confirm risk to a disaster is called milling and is considered the most crucial component in an individual's decision-making process. One of the risks of social media as one of these information sources is that it may lead to a change in the milling process, potentially altering response and actions (Bowser & Cutter, 2015). The more people believe their own knowledge is adequate, the more willing they are to make their own decisions rather than referring to official sources of information (Bowser & Cutter, 2015).

A study conducted in Florida in 2017 examined the relationship between social connections (i.e., perceived access to resources) and evacuation decision making, and concluded that the perceived dependability of an individual's social connections played a significant role in their decision whether to evacuate. People who have more perceived support from their local communities tend not to evacuate (Collins et al., 2017). Other studies support these findings and show people will do what feels best for them even if authorities say otherwise, decreasing their likelihood of evacuation (Dash & Galdwin, 2007). Despite this extensive research on the effects of social networks and awareness, little research has looked at the role social media plays in these decisions.

Misinformation during times of crises

Researchers refer to misinformation as information that is false but disseminated by people that believe it is true (Wardle & Derakhshan, 2018). Conversely, disinformation is information that is also false but disseminated by people that know it is inaccurate and is spread with malicious intent (Wardle & Derakhshan, 2018).

Understanding the intent behind false information is difficult as techniques for differentiating between honest mistakes, deliberate deception and satire are inadequate. The people that spread this information, such as trolls or bots, can also conceal their intentions by framing their false information as satire (Giglietto et al., 2019). The development of bots along with enriched online propaganda tactics give the impression that many users are liking a misleading post or inaccurate news and may become a must-read post or article within a network of believers of certain conspiracy theories and shared as a legitimate source of news (Giglietto et al., 2019). How individuals in these networks determine whether information is informative or uninformative is determined by their interests, backgrounds, previous knowledge and biases (Giglietto et al., 2019). The credibility of the rumors or misinformation they share does not come from direct evidence but rather the fact that they believe it to be true.

This kind of false information has proven to be harmful during crisis events, especially given the importance of accurate emergency communications for affected populations to make informed decisions around disaster response and potential evacuation (Hunt et al., 2020). One example of a misinformation harm during a crisis occurred in 2012, when Hurricane Sandy made landfall in New York City. A meteorologist informed CNN that the first floor of the New York Stock Exchange was flooded under 3 feet of water. This information turned out to be false, and a NYSE official denied the flooding. The misinformation that had been disseminated through the news and social media created a panic amongst the public as potential damage to the New York Stock Exchange could have led to an economic hit (Hunt et al., 2020).

Another example of a misinformation harm occurred during Hurricane Harvey in 2017 when a rumor was spread on Twitter that shelters in Houston, Texas was checking for immigration status and ICE and Customs Border Patrol were going to deter undocumented immigrants from evacuating. This led to widespread confusion amongst people in the Houston metropolitan area, and while officials held multiple press conferences and debunked the rumor, it was still being circulated online towards the final days of the storm (Cheong & Babcock, 2020; Tran et al., 2020).

The misinformation that spreads the fastest is that which overlays a conspiracy with a kernel of truth or a true event, and this spread is facilitated by like-minded individuals whose ideological beliefs and perspectives align with this partisan information (Rojecki & Meraz, 2016). Such with the cases of Hurricane Harvey, Hurricane Sandy, and the flooding of the New York City Stock Exchange, there was a mix of conversations from widespread users that overlaid each other over the course of the crises. This led to users taking specific information out of context and propagating false information, resulting in uninformed decision making (Cheong & Babcock, 2020).

While there has been extensive research around behaviors during hurricanes and how people interpret warning information, there has been limited focus on how the false information that circulates online can influence risk perceptions during extreme weather events. The events that result from misinformed users and their behaviors has been a larger focus of studies on false and problematic information. For example, how propaganda and disinformation campaigns have influenced U.S. political systems such as the 2016 presidential election or the attempted coup on January 6, 2021 (Jack, 2017; Lee et al., 2021; Nkonde et al., 2021). The collective narratives and disinformation that

instigated these events resonated with people because of their lived experiences, and because they were propagated by influential people and accounts across multiple large social media platforms (Lee et al., 2021). The widespread skepticism around the science behind COVID-19 restrictions including mask mandates and lockdowns is another significant example of a shared collective experience that has been widely studied (Lee et al., 2021; Pennycook, 2020). Despite this work, there has not been as much research on the conflation of false information circulation on social media during extreme weather events, risk perceptions, and disaster planning and evacuation decisions.

Twitter and other social media applications were not meant to be crisis communication platforms, yet people have still utilized them for communal sensemaking, in which people practice collective intelligence and social creativity to cope with a natural disaster (Shaw et al., 2013). People want to stay updated during a crisis and rely on social media as a trusted source of information (Hunt et al., 2020; Lin et al., 2016). The use of social media mobile applications is especially popular amongst individuals during a crisis, and allows them to share information as events unfold, sometimes before authorities and the mass media (Houston et al., 2014). Facebook, WhatsApp, and Twitter have been identified in research as the platforms that are the most used during these events, as well as the apps that spread the most misinformation during crises (Tran et al., 2020).

In the context of credibility on social media, studies have shown some users perceive bots as credible as human users, and cannot perceive differences in source credibility, communication competence, or interactional intentions between bots and human users. (Edwards et al., 2013). Studies on rumor response behaviors have found

that social media users are notoriously poor at rumor detection during disasters, mostly due to their truth-biased characters as people are more likely to believe messages are true than to detect any falsehoods or misinformation (Wang & Zhuang, 2018). Research has also shown that Twitter users are more likely to rush to share unverified information, rather than any rumor-debunking information. People tend to believe stories and information that align with their perceptions and view of the world, and turn to these sources to validate their beliefs, a process known as confirmation bias (Giglietto et al., 2019; Wang & Zhuang, 2018).

Social media has been researched extensively as a tool for crisis communication for both organizations and individuals. There has been a limited focus on its potential to lower peoples' risk perceptions due to misinformation, and whether this influences their decision to follow evacuation orders during a natural disaster. This study seeks to address this gap in literature by researching Eastern North Carolinians' use of social media and whether it affects their evacuation decision-making.

DATA & METHODS

The primary research method was an online questionnaire, which was distributed on Facebook and utilized Facebook advertising to increase participation. Participants were also recruited through email listservs, including the master's listserv for the School of Information and Library Science. The incentive for completing the survey was a drawing for a \$100 Amazon gift card. Potential participants were identified as residents of the 44 counties within the Eastern District of North Carolina. While the use of social media as a recruitment tool added bias to the study, the recruitment of participants from a specific geographic area in North Carolina who use social media provided a restricted context that makes the results valid and useful (Black, 2010). Social media use was defined as the use of SNS (social networking sites) and applications, and instant messaging (Correa et al., 2009).

The survey was created using Qualtrics and consisted of questions about participants' social media habits, their perception of risk to extreme weather events, how they use social media to decide whether to follow evacuation orders, and their trust in authorities during a crisis. It also had two open-ended questions that assessed the types of natural disasters participants have evacuated for and the biggest factor in their evacuation decision making. A total of 76 responses were recorded. Most of the data was analyzed quantitatively apart from two open-ended questions.

Participants from the survey are from 27 different Eastern North Carolina counties, and most have lived in this region for more than half their lives.

Chart 1.

66% of participants are between the ages of 55 and 65+ (*Chart 1*). The remaining 34% of participants are divided between the ages of 18 and 54. 96% of participants are white, 3% are Black or African American, and 1% are white and American Indian or Alaska Native. 93% of participants are also female.

Chart 2.

Participants' income is relatively evenly divided between \$25,000 and over \$100,000 (*Chart 2*). 78% of participants are homeowners and 12% are renters. The remaining 10% participants either live at home with family, own a condo/townhouse, or live in a dorm. 45% live with a partner, 25% live with a partner and children, and 20% are single and living alone. The remaining 5% participants live with roommates, with parents, or with children as a single parent.

RESULTS

Housing type and structure can influence evacuation decisions and perceptions of risk. Homeowners are more likely to shelter in place to protect their property, especially during weaker hurricanes, while renters are more likely to leave (Bowser & Cutter, 2015). Out of the participants that have never evacuated, 72% are homeowners. The remaining 28% are divided between renters, living at home with family, living in a dorm, and condo/townhouse owners. Out of the participants that have evacuated, 83% are homeowners. The remaining 17% are divided between renters and condo/townhouse owners. Homeownership rates remain high amongst participants regardless of evacuation status, demonstrating that while homeownership may not be conditional for evacuation decisions for these participants, it may still be a factor in their final decision whether to stay or go. Some participants cited concerns about property damage and looting if they left their homes during a hurricane.

Evacuation is not an option for some participants due to the financial costs of temporary relocation or the potential loss of income. One participant cited not being able to afford a hotel room for a single night as the biggest factor for why they don't evacuate. 43% of participants with an income between \$0-24,999 are able to relocate temporarily, and loss of income is not a factor for 71% of them. More than 90% of participants with incomes between \$25,000 and \$99,999 can temporarily relocate, and for 80% of these

same participants, loss of income is not a factor. Interestingly, the rate of participants that can evacuate without losing income and temporarily relocate decreases with participants who have incomes over \$100,000. Loss of income is not a factor for 56% of them, and 69% are able to temporarily relocate. Research on evacuation decision making shows that people with fewer resources may have a harder time evacuating (Bowser & Cutter, 2015), and such is the case for participants with lower incomes. Overall, 68% of participants can evacuate without losing income as well as relocate temporarily. Out of these participants, 60% have evacuated.

Chart 3.

Facebook is the most used social media application by all participants (*Chart 3*). Participants ages 18-24 use it about as often as other applications like Instagram and Snapchat. As age increases, the popularity of other applications decreases in favor of Facebook. For participants ages 55-65+ Facebook is the primary social media application they use most frequently. This is also indicative in the demographics of the participants who completed the survey. As the primary method of recruitment was Facebook

advertising, this may explain why the age demographics of more than half of participants were skewed towards older populations, as well as white and female.

According to the Pew Research Center, Facebook remains one of the most widely used social media applications in the U.S. (Auxier & Anderson, 2021). It is used by more than 60% of White, Black, and Hispanic Americans, and is more widely used by women than men (Auxier & Anderson, 2021). Facebook and YouTube remain the two most used platforms among populations 65 and older (Auxier & Anderson, 2021). More than 70% of people ages 30-49 and 50-64 use Facebook, compared to approximately 70% of people ages 18-29. Instagram, Snapchat and TikTok are especially popular among young adults. More than 60% use Instagram and Snapchat, while approximately half use TikTok (Auxier & Anderson, 2021).

Results from the survey indicate participants use social media more frequently to seek information when preparing for a disaster than for evacuation decisions. Some participants that said they do not use social media for evacuation decision making said they use other information sources, such as news outlets or weather authorities. Studies have shown that people who rely on a variety of media sources (i.e., radio, television, and social media) are more likely to evacuate (Sadri et al. 2017).

47% of participants reported never evacuating. Of those participants, 94% use social media for disaster preparation, and 83% use it for evacuation decisions. Of the 53% of participants that have evacuated, 90% use social media for disaster preparation, and 78% use it for evacuation decisions. Studies have shown there is a personalization effect during evacuation decision-making that influences how people make intuitive judgements and turn perceptions of risk into concrete personalized assessments (Sadri et

al., 2017). During this process, people seek information from different sources, including social media (Bowser & Cutter, 2015; Dash & Galdwin, 2007). Participants that don't evacuate and use social media to make these decisions are incorporating these information sources as part of their personalized assessments and making a judgement that disasters do not pose enough risk to them to consider evacuation. Research has shown that sole reliance on the Internet for information, as well as for weather-related information, makes people less likely to evacuate (Sadri et al., 2017).

Chart 4.

92% of participants use social media to prepare for natural disasters. When adjusted by age, social media use is lowest for disaster preparedness for ages 35-44 (80%), closely followed by people ages 18-24 (86%) (*Chart 4*). Social media use is highest for ages 25-34 (100%) and 45-54 (100%). Social media use is also high for ages 55-64 and 65+.

Chart 5.

80% of participants use social media for evacuation decisions. When adjusted by age, social media use is lowest for ages 35-44 (60%), followed by people ages 55-64 (76%) (*Chart 5*). More than 80% of participants ages 18-24 and 45-54 use social media for evacuation decisions. Notably, social media use is highest for participants ages 25-34 (100%).

Of the participants that have never evacuated, the top 3 social media apps used for natural disaster preparation and evacuation decisions include Facebook, Instagram, and Pinterest. Of the participants that have evacuated, the top 3 social media apps used for natural disaster preparation and evacuation decisions include Facebook, Twitter, and Instagram. The wide use of Facebook for disaster response and planning by participants aligns with the Pew Research Center's findings that Facebook is the most used social media platform for news (Gramlich, 2021) as well as one of the most used apps during a disaster (Tran et al., 2020).

Chart 6.

Results from the study show people in Eastern North Carolina are concerned with the impacts of natural disasters in their counties, including property damage, loss of life, and economic impacts. 45% of participants said they are “very concerned” about these impacts where they live. Only 2% said they were “not concerned.” People are also noticing changes in their environment. Changes in precipitation patterns and air or water temperatures have been seen by at least 50% of participants (*Chart 6*). Only 12% of participants have not noticed any changes in environmental conditions where they live. These results indicate most participants do perceive they are at risk to disasters where they live, and that there have been changes in environmental conditions. It’s plausible the changes they are noticing contribute to their perception of risk to disasters, particularly for participants who are noticing precipitation changes.

Chart 7.

Nearly 100% of participants have experienced hurricanes, tropical storms, and severe storms (*Chart 7*). Most participants also experienced flooding and excessive temperatures, while almost half experienced tornadoes. Given the length of time participants have lived in their respective counties and the recent history of hurricanes and flooding within Eastern North Carolina, the results in *Chart 2* are not surprising. What is interesting is how this experience is possibly influencing evacuation decisions. While participants are concerned about natural disasters and changing environment conditions, almost half still do not evacuate. It's certainly possible that this previous experience changed some participants' perceptions of risk to future events and increased their confidence in their ability to ride out storms (Resnick, 2018). When it comes to information seeking, these same participants are relying on social media as part of their evacuation decision making process, including various weather blogs and Facebook pages. Ultimately, these participants are deciding to do what feels best for them,

sometimes in contradiction to what authorities are telling them to do and are utilizing social media to make these decisions (Dash & Galdwin, 2007).

there are also participants that do not consider evacuating whatsoever. It is important to note that for these participants, the decision to evacuate is not dependent on any specific information sources because they simply have no plan to evacuate. 41% of participants say they do not have an evacuation plan, and 58% of these participants have never evacuated. These results support findings from past studies that indicate people with a definite evacuation plan are more likely to evacuate than those who don't have one (Burnside et al., 2007).

For one participant, they indicated they would not be able to find temporary shelter, and said after Floyd, it's "best to stay home." Another participant stated that it is "Perfect to stay home. Too difficult to return." Two participants said they work for their county or municipality in some disaster response capacity. One said they're required to stay in their county to work shelters, but that they would evacuate their family if the hurricane were stronger than a category 2. The other participant, an emergency manager for their municipality, said they use "NWS, HURREVAC, and other reliable sources"; and that social media is "the absolute worst resource." Remaining participants that do not use social media for evacuation decisions said they consider the projected strength of the storm, predicted storm surge and wind speeds, personal safety, the safety of their family, and whether their partner would evacuate.

When asked what the biggest factor is in their evacuation decision making, participants gave a wide range of answers from the strength of the storm to the safety of their families. Some participants expressed concern about not being able to return if they

evacuated and cited it as the reason they usually don't evacuate. One participant said, "do not leave because officials take way too long to let folks come back." Reentry after a hurricane is still an understudied area with conflicting evidence, particularly around the thought process behind returning home and how this affects evacuation decisions. As the evacuation response process is multidimensional, when to return is considered a factor that influences hurricane decision making (Bowser & Cutter, 2015). Studies that have focused on reentry and its effect on evacuation decision making are conflicted, however some research has indicated that people who experienced delays due to media reporting would be more reluctant to leave next time (Bowser & Cutter, 2015). The participants that are reluctant to leave again due to poor experiences with reentry cited a couple different reasons, including delays from government officials to lift the evacuation order and damage from the hurricane making it impossible to return home.

Many participants said they considered the strength of the storm as their biggest factor for evacuating. Some participants use specific categories to determine whether they'll evacuate. One participant said they would only evacuate for a Category 4 or 5 hurricane, and another said they would only stay for a "high Cat 1/ low 2." Participants also said they consider "projected strength of storm", "severity of the storm", "wind strength", "Forecast wind speed and hurricane track", and "what level hurricane is and where it's landing." Reliance on the Saffir-Simpson scale for evacuation decisions is problematic, as people are less likely to evacuate for hurricanes that they believe are weak (Bowser & Cutter, 2015). Even smaller systems can cause significant damage, as seen during Hurricane Florence, which made landfall as a Category 1 but caused approximately \$22 billion in damage (Williams, 2019).

Out of the participants that said their biggest factor for evacuating was the category or strength of the storm, almost all use Facebook and various weather blogs as their main sources of information. While some participants use weather blogs and Facebook pages that are from official sources like meteorologists and weather authorities, some of the blogs and pages are not managed by these sources. 20% of participants use a blog and Facebook page called “Mike’s Weather Page,” which is managed by its creator Mike Boylan and has over 1 million followers. Boylan is not a meteorologist and tells people to refer to professionals for advice about “putting up shutters or evacuating (Frisaro, 2021).” On his Facebook page and website, Mike seems to rely heavily on weather data and satellite imagery from NOAA, as well as the National Hurricane Center (NHC) and National Weather Service (NWS) (Boylan, *Mike's Weather Page*).

Another blog used by participants is “Tropical Tidbits,” run by Levi Cowan, who states on his blog that his “forecasts do not represent the prognostications of any government office” and to visit the National Hurricane Center for official information (Cowan, 2012). On his “About” page he says he has a Ph.D. in Meteorology from Florida State University. Levi seems to primarily use data from NOAA, including satellite imagery and forecast models. A few other sources include the NHC, the Meteorological Service of Canada, the Global Ocean Data Assimilation Experiment, and the European Center for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (Cowan, 2012).

According to Rick Knabb, a chief meteorologist at The Weather Channel, weather bloggers are helpful sources of information “as long as they relay official National Weather Service information, along with instructions from local and state emergency managers (Frisaro, 2021).” While these specific blogs reportedly use official information,

this information is being interpreted by people outside crisis authorities or non-professionals, and their interpretations may not perfectly align with the recommendations of local and state emergency managers. Such is the case with anti-mask groups who use data provided by local and state health departments to create “counter visualizations” to challenge the science behind mask mandates and lockdowns (Lee et al., 2021). The formation of the anti-mask groups and its subculture is shaped by mistrust in institutional authorities and orthodox scientific viewpoints, and value individual ingenuity and initiative. They only trust the scientific analysis that they can replicate themselves with data they can manipulate firsthand and resent analysis from “scientific elites” (Lee et al., 2021).

Some participants use these blogs along with more official information sources; however, others listed the blogs as their sole source of information. Some simply listed “Facebook.” Considering the lens through which these participants interpret warning information (i.e., strength of storm, track of hurricane) and their use of unofficial sources, previous research suggests that the participants may believe their own knowledge will suffice and are more likely to make their own decisions than to refer to officials (Bowser & Cutter, 2015; Dash & Galdwin, 2007).

The results from this study demonstrate that social media use is part of the disaster planning and evacuation decision making for most participants, and some of the most used apps for this process include Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, and Pinterest. While some participants use official sources like NOAA, NWS, and other weather authorities; others exclusively use Facebook and weather blogs run by non-crisis authorities, potentially influencing their perceptions of risk to incoming disasters.

Additionally, many participants cited reliance on the Saffir-Simpson scale as the biggest factor behind evacuation decision making, demonstrating a potential issue as reliance on this scale is extremely risky (Bowser & Cutter, 2015). Participants that had difficulty returning after evacuating said they would rather stay home for future hurricanes, signifying the need for more research into the return process and what specific factors are dissuading people from evacuating again.

The use of Facebook advertising as one of the main methods of recruiting may be the reason why participants are more inclined to use Facebook, and why they might be more likely to check social media. Although recruitment was conducted within a wide geographic area, the number of people that responded to the survey was still small, and its demographics were skewed towards older, white and female. The conclusions drawn based on results from the survey had to be limited to that of the population surveyed, rather than that of the entire population in Eastern North Carolina. While results aligned with findings from similar studies, they also created more questions, demonstrating further study is needed on the evacuation decision making process of people in high-risk areas like Eastern North Carolina.

CONCLUSION

Research on the influence of misinformation from social media on risk perceptions during disasters and subsequent disaster response behavior is limited. The results from this study seek to address this gap in research, provide contextual evidence to support findings from previous research done on evacuation decision making behavior, and identify next steps for future research on this topic.

Results from the survey show that participants with a poor experience evacuating have less trust in crisis authorities and prefer to stay home for future disasters. These participants cited the delay returning to their home as the main reason behind their dissatisfaction. Previous research has observed that some people change their evacuation response behavior if a disaster does not affect their area as predicted (Baker et al., 2012; Bowser & Cutter, 2015; Sims & Baumann, 1983). The findings in this study demonstrate there may be additional reasons why people that evacuate for one disaster change their response for another, and that future research could help clarify this phenomenon.

Next steps for future research on evacuation decision making include interviews with people in high-risk areas to get a more in-depth look at the social media habits of people that don't evacuate, the kind of information they trust and why. Future studies could also assess high-risk populations' trust in crisis authorities and government and compare the results to a similar assessment conducted with people in low-risk areas.

The evacuation decision making process is multidimensional and consists of various personal, social, and experiential factors (Bowser & Cutter, 2015). People

personalize their risk to crises by seeking information from different sources, and the use of social media risks changing the milling process, potentially altering perceptions of risk and decreasing likelihood of evacuation (Bowser & Cutter, 2015; Dash & Galdwin, 2007; Sadri et al., 2017). More research is needed on hurricane behaviors and evacuation decision making, and how social media is shaping affected populations' perceptions of risk.

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APPENDICES

APPENDIX A: SURVEY

When Hurricanes Go Viral

Start of Block: Informed Consent

Q1 Welcome to the When Hurricanes Go Viral Research Study!

University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill Research Information Sheet
IRB Study #: 21-1328
Principal Investigator: Rachel O'Reilly

The purpose of this research study is to investigate how residents of Eastern North Carolina use social media to prepare for natural disasters. You are being asked to take part in a research study because you reside within Eastern North Carolina and use social media.

Being in a research study is completely voluntary. You can choose not to be in this research study. You can also say yes now and change your mind later.

If you agree to take part in this research, you will be asked to answer a series of survey questions, with a mix of multiple-choice and open-ended questions. You will be asked to provide your county of residence in the survey, as well as your email to be entered in a drawing for a \$100 Amazon gift card. Your email address is not required to participate in the survey, and entry in the drawing is voluntary. You will also be asked while taking the survey if you wish to participate in a follow-up interview. The survey will take about 15-20 minutes to complete. If you choose to participate in the interview, you will be asked to provide your name, and will receive an email to schedule a time for the interview. The interview will take place over Zoom.

This study information sheet serves as a consent form. A consent addendum for communication and audiovisual recording will be provided prior to the interview for you to sign. An interview guide will also be provided prior to the interview. The interview will take about 30-35 minutes to conduct. After the interview you will be entered in an additional drawing for a \$50 Amazon gift card. We expect that 50 people will take part in this research study.

You can choose to stop taking the survey at any time. You must be at least 18 years old to participate. If you are younger than 18 years old, please stop now.

Potential risks for completing this survey include consequences of a breach of confidentiality. To protect your identity as a research subject, the research data will be coded and converted to pseudonyms and the researcher will not share your information with anyone. In any publication about this research, your name or other private information will not be used.

If you have any questions about this research, please contact the Investigator named at the top of this form by emailing rachelrr@live.unc.edu. If you have questions or concerns about your rights as a research subject, you may contact the UNC Institutional Review Board at 919-966-3113 or by email to IRB_subjects@unc.edu.

- I consent, begin the study (1)
- I do not consent, I do not wish to participate (2)

End of Block: Informed Consent

Start of Block: Eligibility Questions

Q2 What county in Eastern, North Carolina do you live in? (Options are limited to the 44 counties within Eastern, North Carolina according to the United States District Court for the Eastern District of North Carolina:

<https://www.nced.uscourts.gov/counties/Default.aspx>. If your county is not on this list you will not be considered eligible to take this survey.)

▼ Beaufort (1) ... Wilson (44)

Q3 If you would like to be entered in the drawing for the \$100 Amazon gift card, please enter your email below.

End of Block: Eligibility Questions

Start of Block: Survey Questions

Q5 Which age group are you in?

- 18-24 (1)
 - 25-34 (2)
 - 35-44 (3)
 - 45-54 (4)
 - 55-64 (5)
 - 65 or older (6)
 - Prefer not to answer (7)
-

Q6 What is your gender identity?

- Female (1)
 - Male (2)
 - Transgender Female (3)
 - Transgender Male (4)
 - Non-binary (5)
 - Not listed (specify below) (6)

 - Prefer not to answer (7)
-

Q7 Choose one or more races that you consider yourself to be:

- White (1)
- Black or African American (2)
- American Indian or Alaska Native (3)
- Asian (4)
- Native Hawaiian or Pacific Islander (5)
- Other (6) _____
- Prefer not to answer (7)
-

Q8 Are you Spanish, Hispanic, or Latine or none of these?

- Yes (1)
- None of these (2)
- Prefer not to answer (3)
-

Q9 Which of the following best describes the situation where you live? (please choose one)

- Own a house (1)
 - Rent a house (2)
 - Own a condominium or townhouse (3)
 - Rent an apartment (4)
 - Live in a dorm (5)
 - Live at home with family (6)
 - Other (please specify) (7)
-

Prefer not to answer (8)

Q10 Which of the following best describes your household composition? (please choose one)

- Single/living alone (1)
 - Live with roommates (2)
 - Live with parents (3)
 - Live with a partner (4)
 - Live with a partner and children (5)
 - Live with children/single parent household (6)
 - Other (please specify) (7)
-

Prefer not to answer (10)

Q11 Which one of the following categories do you think best describes your yearly household income?

- 0–24,999 (1)
 - 25,000–49,999 (2)
 - 50,000–74,999 (3)
 - 75,000–99,999 (4)
 - Over 100,000 (5)
 - Prefer not to answer (6)
-

Q12 Which best reflects the highest level of education you have completed?

- High School Diploma (1)
 - College Degree (2- or 4-year) (2)
 - Graduate Degree (master's, PhD., etc.) (3)
 - Currently in college (undergraduate) (4)
 - Currently in college (graduate) (5)
 - None of the above (6)
 - Prefer not to answer (7)
-

Q13 How long have you lived in your current county of residence?

- Fill in the blank (1) _____
- Prefer not to answer (2)
-

Q14 Have you noticed any changes in the following environmental conditions where you live? (check all that apply)

- precipitation patterns (storm frequency, storm intensity, rainfall amounts) (1)
- air or water temperature (2)
- erosion rates (3)
- water/tide level (4)
- landscape/vegetation (5)
- Other (please specify) (6)
-
- Not applicable (7)
-

Q15 In your lifetime, which of the following types of natural hazards have you experienced? (check all that apply)

- Flooding (2)
 - Hurricane/tropical storm (3)
 - Severe storms (wind, lightning, hail) (9)
 - Tornado/cyclone (11)
 - Excessive temperatures (12)
 - Groundwater contamination (13)
 - Other (please specify) (17)
-

Q16 Which of the following types of natural hazards are possible in your current county?
(check all that apply)

- Flooding (2)
 - Hurricane/tropical storm (3)
 - Severe storms (wind, lightning, hail) (9)
 - Tornado/cyclone (11)
 - Excessive temperatures (12)
 - Groundwater contamination (13)
 - Other (please specify) (17)
-

Q17 How concerned are you about the impacts of natural hazards in your current county
(e.g., property damage, loss of life, economic impacts, etc.)?

- Not concerned (1)
 - Somewhat concerned (2)
 - Very concerned (3)
 - Extremely concerned (18)
-

Q18 Do you feel prepared for a natural disaster?

- Definitely yes (1)
 - Probably yes (2)
 - Probably not (3)
 - Definitely not (4)
-

Q19 If a hurricane were forecasted, what would you do (check all that apply)?

- Evacuate if told to do so. (1)
 - Take steps to protect your home/business (i.e. retrofitting, sandbags, wood on windows) (2)
 - Review your insurance policies (3)
 - Purchase non-perishable emergency supplies (4)
 - Other (please specify) (5)
-
- I don't know (6)
-

Q20 Have you ever participated in a natural hazard drill or community awareness/preparedness exercise regarding the following natural hazards? (check all that apply)

- Flooding (4)
 - Hurricane/tropical storm (5)
 - Flooding (6)
 - Severe storms (wind, lightning, hail) (9)
 - Tornado/cyclone (10)
 - Excessive temperatures (11)
 - Groundwater contamination (12)
 - Other (please specify) (8)
-
- Not applicable (13)

Q21 Do you have an emergency kit?

- Yes (1)
- No (2)
- I don't know (3)

Q22 Which of the following emergency supplies do you have readily available? (check all that apply)

- Bottled water (1)
 - Non-perishable food (2)
 - First aid kit (3)
 - Radio and batteries (4)
 - Dust masks (5)
 - Gasoline (6)
 - Evacuation plan (7)
 - Other (please specify) (9)
-

- None (8)
-

Q23 Please rank how prepared you are for the probable impacts of natural hazard events likely to occur in your county. Rank on a scale of 1 to 5 (1 representing the least prepared to 5 representing the most prepared or NA- Not applicable).

Not Applicable

1 2 3 4 5

Power outage ()	
No clean water ()	
Inhibited transportation ()	
Lack of access to stores ()	
Lack of access to emergency services ()	
Lack of access to banks and ATM's ()	

Q24 Which social media applications do you use? (check all that apply)

- Twitter (1)
 - Instagram (2)
 - Facebook (3)
 - Snapchat (4)
 - YouTube (5)
 - WhatsApp (6)
 - Pinterest (7)
 - LinkedIn (8)
 - Tik Tok (9)
 - Other (please specify) (10)

 - None (11)
-

Q25 Is there a certain social media app you prefer over others? (Choose top three)

- Twitter (1)
 - Instagram (2)
 - Facebook (3)
 - Snapchat (4)
 - YouTube (5)
 - WhatsApp (6)
 - Pinterest (7)
 - LinkedIn (8)
 - Tik Tok (9)
 - Other (please specify) (10)
-

None (11)

Q26 How frequently do you use social media when preparing for a natural disaster, such as a hurricane?

- Several times a day (1)
 - About once a day (2)
 - Several times a week (3)
 - About once a week (4)
 - Less often (5)
 - Never (6)
-

Q27 How frequently do you use social media when deciding whether to evacuate for a natural disaster?

- Several times a day (1)
 - About once a day (2)
 - Several times a week (3)
 - About once a week (4)
 - Less often (5)
 - Never (6)
-

Q28 To the best of your ability, please list the accounts on social media you primarily follow during a natural disaster. Feel free to include accounts across different platforms (i.e. accounts you follow on Twitter and Facebook)

- Click to write Choice 1 (1)
-

Q29 When you moved to North Carolina, did you consider the possible occurrence of natural hazards where you moved?

- Yes (1)
 - No (2)
 - Don't know (3)
 - Not applicable (4)
-

Q30 If you answered “no” to the previous question, would knowing more about local natural hazards have influenced your decision to move to this area?

- Yes (1)
 - No (2)
 - Don't know (3)
 - Not applicable (4)
-

Q31 Have you ever evacuated for a natural disaster?

- Yes (1)
 - No (2)
 - Don't know (3)
-

Q32 To the best of your ability, please list the natural disasters you have evacuated for.

- List natural disasters in text entry box (4)

Q33 Is loss of income a factor in choosing whether to evacuate for a natural disaster?

- Yes (1)
- No (2)
- Don't know (3)

Q34 Are you able to temporarily relocate during a natural disaster?

- Yes (1)
- No (2)
- Don't know (3)

Q35 What would you say is the biggest factor in your final decision when choosing whether to evacuate?
